

Assessment of Acceptability of Covid-19 Vaccine among the Health Workers and Vaccine Recipients in Part of FCT Abuja, Nigeria.

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Abstract

Covid-19 is a pandemic of acute respiratory disease that was first detected and identified in late December in China in 2019. Due to increased concerns because of cases outside China and increased incidence in China, the World Health Organization (WHO) declared the disease as a pandemic and public health emergency. Since its emergence, the number of daily confirmed cases of COVID-19 worldwide has increased dramatically. The virus causes morbidity in many millions of people and has taken the lives of many millions since its emergence. The situation was similar in Nigeria; soon after the first case was detected in Nigeria on (27th February 2020), the incidence increased. In countries such as Nigeria, the transmissibility of the virus is high due to overcrowding and poor socioeconomic status. The possibility of pandemics in Nigeria is more likely due to poor infrastructure, weak health systems, large household size, inadequate sanitation, population turnover from site to site or increased mobility. The number of COVID-19 cases in Nigeria has continued to increase. For instance, the total number of COVID-19 cases within a country is higher than expected. The mortality from the disease within a country is also high, which is attributed to the disease. However, the total number of cases detected in Nigeria may have been underestimated because of insufficient testing capacity and attitude of people about the pandemic. A 30-item questionnaire was used as a primary tool in which the questions related to; knowledge, attitude, willingness to accept Covid-19 vaccine and its adverse effect were asked, 200 of such questionnaires were administered to various healthcare

workers and community vaccine recipients through a random sampling method using cross sectional descriptive study. The hard copy of the instrument (questionnaire) was translated into a soft copy of online Google form which was used to collect the Data from respondents and auto analyzed them. The analyzed Data were moved from the Google form into Microsoft word for reporting and discussion using the Snipping tool and Microsoft paint where necessary to organize the data which must be coded in the code book before reporting in the Microsoft word page. The study was conducted over a period of eight weeks. Out of the 200(100%) respondents 120(60%) were community vaccine recipients, whereas 24(12%) received their vaccine in Asokoro District Hospital and 21(10.5%) received the vaccine in Nyanya General Hospital. It was also demonstrates that 200 (100%) of the participants who participated in the study completed the questionnaire which was given to them and it was analyzed. 107 (53.5%) of the respondents received the vaccine based on the public advice on the vaccination provided by the World Health Organization, while 67 (33.5%) were convinced by the political will, community and religious leaders who received the vaccination, and families and friends played a role in influencing others with about 47 (23.5%) out of the two hundred. National primary health care development agency should work hand in hand with the Asokoro District Hospital/Nyanya general hospital to seek the political well to increase the Covid-19 vaccine rollout and to encourage vaccination of the populace. Covid-19 Vaccine should be made available and accessible including the booster to encourage the vaccination in order to curb the spread of the disease in federal capital territory. Media Such as television and radio should be used to inform and encourage the federal capital territory and it environ about the Covid-19 vaccine and its safety. The international bodies such as World Health Organizations (W.H.O), United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) and other Non-Governmental Organizations(NGOs) should help the federal capital territory (FCT) with the Covid-19 vaccine and also policies on how to get populace of the federal capital territory vaccinated.

Keywords: Assessment, Covid-19 Vaccine, Health Workers, Vaccine Recipients, FCT, Abuja

1. INTRODUCTION

The Covid-19 epidemic, an acute respiratory infection that was first discovered in late December 2019 in Wuhan China, is presently wreaking havoc on the whole world. The World Health Organization (WHO) declared the sickness a pandemic and a public health emergency of global concern as a consequence of mounting concerns over cases outside of China and an increase in its prevalence there. Since it originally surfaced, the daily verified COVID-19 case count has dramatically increased. The virus has infected millions of people since it was first discovered and killed millions more. Similar conditions were present in Nigeria, where the frequency quickly increased after the country's first case was identified on February 27, 2020. The virus is very contagious in countries like Nigeria because of overcrowding and bad socioeconomic conditions. Inadequate infrastructure, weak healthcare systems, high family sizes, poor sanitation, population migration from place to place, all increase the danger of pandemics in Nigeria. The incidence of COVID-19 has been continuously increasing in Nigeria.

1.1 Statement of problem

Although immunizations are crucial for preventing the spread of infectious and communicable illnesses, there are several complications that can occur when giving vaccines to members of the general public who qualify for them. For instance, a lot of individuals think the Covid-19 vaccination is a hoax. Unawareness, which includes a lack of accurate information and a casual attitude toward the epidemic as a whole, may be the largest problem. Some people may decide not to get vaccinated due to the vaccines' inadequacy. mRNA vaccine particularly that of Covid-19 have been associated to myocarditis and other serious side effects, however these incidents are rare. Patients who had certain malignancies or who had recently had cancer treatment were particularly vulnerable. These findings emphasize the need of cancer patients maintaining mitigation practices, especially in light of the emergence of novel virus types and the declining efficacy of immunizations.

1.2 Aims and objectives of the study

To evaluate community vaccine recipients' attitudes toward the Covid-19 vaccine and the knowledge of healthcare professionals.

To ascertain whether some individuals accepted the vaccine after being coerced by their community leaders or under threat of losing their jobs.

The research work help to evaluate the vaccine's accessibility, in particular front-line medical staff.

The study helps to gauge the community's and healthcare workers' willingness to accept the Covid-19 vaccine

The research also provided us with the data about negative effects of the Covid-19 vaccine on community vaccine recipients and healthcare professionals.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Compared to the general population, medical professionals are more prone to get COVID-19. Since health workers are more likely to contract COVID-19 than the general population, several nations organise vaccination programmes for them. But not everybody embraces the immunization in the same manner.

How well immunization programmes are received by the general public has a significant impact on the success of the global effort to eradicate the disease. Delay, hesitation, and refusal are all examples of vaccination rejection.

Covid-19 vaccination programmes, which are already under way in some countries, may face any of the aforementioned challenges, especially due to the novelty of the disease, perceived controversies related to its origin, and the fast-tracked development of the disease.

The belief that the virus cannot thrive in hot climates causes people to continue to deny the existence of the disease in some tropical areas, such as Nigeria. This study is expected to identify potential obstacles to the effectiveness of a COVID-19 vaccination programme and provide guidance for the program's further development and implementation.

Halimat, Olugbake and Shakirat, reported that out of 1063 forms that were obtained in total of research they conducted only 1058 of them were finished and analysed. There were more male responses (382; 36.1%) than female responses (676; 63.9%). The average age was 40.8 years (40.8 + 12.2) years. 75.7% of the respondents, or 801

people, held bachelor's or master's degrees. There were 594% more workers in the health sector than there were in the non-health sector. Those with full knowledge of COVID-19 and its vaccine, 171 (69.79%) wanted to get immunized as soon as one became available.

2.1 Covid-19 vaccine hesitancy.

Obi Peter Adigwe reported that they were concerned about the COVID-19 vaccination's negative effects and that they may be deterred from being vaccinated as a result. The majority of responders, 85.1%, agreed that citizens should receive the COVID-19 vaccination free of charge. However, 26% of the participants said they would be prepared to pay a charge for the COVID-19 immunization. The motivation to pay for COVID-19 vaccine is greater among older individuals and those who have already contracted the disease.

2.2 Willingness and perception to accept Covid-19 vaccine.

48.6% of responders to a study by Blessing, Josiah, and Marios in the Delta state of Nigeria were willing to get vaccinated. The public had strong understanding about COVID-19 and the vaccination, even though more than half of them were unwilling to receive it.

2.3 Covid-19 Vaccine Doses and Third Booster Dose.

In a research conducted by Moyad, it as found out that 77% of the 614 participants had gotten the first two doses of the COVID-19 vaccination, but only an average of them knew about the third booster dosage, scoring 44.6% with a 95% confidence interval (CI) of [41%, 49%]. Questions concerning whether or not they were aware of the third COVID-19 booster shot were used to gauge awareness about the vaccination.

2.4 Adverse Effects of Covid-19 Vaccine

A small percentage of people occasionally experience mild to moderate side effects following vaccination, but rarely severe ones. The Covid-19 vaccine is not an exception because there have been side effects reported, which are typically mild to moderate and transient. The likelihood of experiencing any of these adverse reactions after vaccination varies depending on the COVID-19 vaccine type. According to a

study conducted in South-South Nigeria by, Peter C. Oriji, Dennis O. Allagoa, Lukman.

Nine out of every ten medical professionals who received the vaccine reported side effects. The majority of side effects (53.2%) began the day after vaccination. 104 vaccine recipients (68.9%) reported experiencing pain at the injection site, the most frequent side effect

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1 Study layout

A cross-sectional descriptive research was conducted to determine how well-informed, open-minded, and eager to embrace the Covid-19 vaccination healthcare professionals at Asokoro District Hospital, Nyanya General Hospital, and community vaccine recipients in Bwari and Abuja Municipal Area Councils-FCT.

3.2 Sample Size

Using the Cochran formula, which indicated that $n = \frac{Z^2pq}{d^2}$, the sample size was determined. Sampling technique, every unit in the population has a chance (non-zero probability) of being picked in the sample, and this chance can be precisely calculated. This is how the probability sampling method was applied.

Of course, a random sampling was employed in this study; as a result, a random sampling is one that is taken from a population of units in a way that gives each member of the population an equal chance of being chosen and allows for the independent selection of various units. Nonetheless, each member of the population is given the same selection probability. By doing this, the investigator may be sure that the population is properly understood and described. Inaccurate influences can be prevented by avoiding biases and over sight for community vaccine recipients stratified random used to cover the population in view for the study, then from each stratum, a random selection of study units is chosen. This technique has the benefit of allowing for the consideration of information on the population's composition in relation to a variety of stratifying variables. If the population's age, sex, and ethnic makeup are known, for example, stratification may be done using these characteristics to choose a sample that closely matches the population's demographics. Despite the

fact that proportion is also taken into account. For the healthcare professionals, I used cluster random sampling approach, which encloses groups of clusters of sample units in a clearly definable border. Cluster formation does not require that the research units inside a "cluster" be identical. To the greatest extent practicable, each cluster should have a roughly equal number of study units. After that, a random sample is drawn from each cluster, for example, from the cluster of clinical doctors, pharmacists, nurses, laboratory technicians, keepers of medical records, and hospital cleaners.

3.3 Sources of data

Primary data was generated through administration of designed questionnaire in English language, which comprises open and semi- Structured questions, the questionnaire was designed to include topic of research, introduction and sections; A, B and C two hundred questionnaires were filled by they responded, the questionnaire was generated based on the objectives of the study.

Section A: consist of Biodata (age, sex, tribe, religion, marital status, academic qualifications, occupation, area of residence and alcohol/tobacco intake).Section B: designed to assess knowledge, attitudes of they responded toward COVID-19 vaccine (exposure to COVID-19, Section C: was designed to assess willingness to accept COVID-19 vaccine (was there threat to accept the COVID-19 vaccine, booster dose and adverse effect of the vaccine).The questionnaire was filled by the responded at their shift and communities also at their convenience.

3.4 Statistical Data Analysis

The hard copy of the instrument (questionnaire) was translated into a soft copy of online Google form which was used to collect the Data from respondents and auto analyzed them. The analyzed Data were moved from the Google form into Microsoft word for reporting and discussion using the Snipping tool and Microsoft paint where necessary to organize the data which must be coded in the code book before reporting in the Microsoft word page

3.5 Consent and moral dilemmas

The Federal Capital Territory Health Research Ethics Committee Research Unit is located in Room 10 of Block A of the HHSS Secretariat at No. 1 Kapital Street 11,

Garki, Abuja, Nigeria. All participants indicated their approval for their replies to be collected, anonymized, and used for research and publishing; only those who did so were automatically sent the survey form.

Age (as at last birthday).

In contrast to a study conducted in southern Nigeria by Peter C. Oriji, which revealed that approximately 52.3% of respondents were female health workers and 49.0% were between the ages of 36 and 45, the data in the chart above shows that the majority of respondents—165, or 82.5%—are under 25 years old. A research conducted in Nigeria by Halima Adedeji-Adenola, Olubusola A. Olugbake and Shakirat A. Adenosine reveals that more women (676, or 63.9%) than men (382, or 36.1%) responded to the survey. 40.8 12.2 years was the average age.

Ethnic group

ETHNIC GROUP	NUMBER OF PARTICIPANTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
HAUSA	35	17.5%
YORUBA	33	16.5%
IGBO	40	20%
GBAGYI	24	12%
KILBA / HOBA	32	16%
OTHER TRIBES	36	18%
GRANT TOTAL	200.	100%

The above table shows that, most of these respondents belong to Igbo ethnicity 40(20%) with a mean score of 33.3, probably due to orientation about Covid-19 vaccination even though the study was carried out in Abuja.

Vaccination centre

VACCINATION CENTRE	NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	PERCENTAGE (%)
ASOKORO	24	12%
COMMUNITY	120	60%
NYANYA G.H	21	10.5%
NATIONAL HOSPITAL	4	2%
NONE	31	15.5%
GRANT TOTAL	200	100%

The table above Shows that, out of the 200(100%) respondents 120(60%) are community vaccine recipients, whereas 24(12%) received their vaccine in Asokoro District Hospital and 21(10.5%) received the vaccine in Nyanya General Hospital

Perception of Covid-19?

PERCEPTION	NUMBER OF RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE
A global health challenge	179	89.5%
A conspiracy	12	6%
A myth	5	2.5%
A Hoax	4	2%
GRANT TOTAL	200	100

The table above shows that the majority of the respondents 179(89.5%) perceive that Covid-19 is a global challenge.

Knowledge about W.H.O

The chart above indicate that out of the 200(100%) 189(94.5%) knows what World Health Organization (W.H.O) stands for, whereas 11(5.5%) doesn't know it.

Threat to accept the vaccine

THREATS	NUMBER OF RESPONSE	PERCENTAGE
Loss of job	25	17.01%
Frontline Healthcare worker	15	10.2%
No threat	100	68.01%
Denial of Visa	3	2.04%
Undecided	4	2.72%
GRAND TOTAL	147	99.98% ~ 100%

The table above shows that 200 forms were shared and analyzed 25(17.01%) were said to have been forced to accept the vaccine because they were scared of losing their jobs, while 15(10.2%) were healthcare workers and as such they must get vaccinated with Covid-19 vaccine as frontline health care workers, whereas 3(2.04%) was because of Visa denial to travel abroad.

Confidence on the safety of the vaccine

Multiple responses, if applicable is allowed.

The graph above demonstrates that 200 (100%) of the participants who participated in the study completed the questionnaire given to them and it was analyzed. 107 (53.5%) of the respondents received the vaccination based on the public advice on the vaccination provided by the World Health Organization, while 67 (33.5%) were convinced by the political will, community and religious leaders who received the vaccination, and families and friends played a role in influencing others with about 47 (23.5%) out of the two hundred.

This is not consistent with research done in the UK by Louisa Manby, Anna Dowrick, and Amelia Kaira. Health care workers (HCWs) were the only group studied, and they mostly claimed that while they felt highly motivated to promote vaccination, they did not feel obligated to do so. Some HCWs reported taking a highly active part in urging their patients to get immunized by "directing them, signposting them to links, calling up patients who have concerns about the vaccine," with the goal of assisting them in making educated decisions regarding immunization.

Patients frequently asked if they had had a vaccination, according to many. They believed that this was due to the fact that patients desired confidence regarding their choice of vaccination from reputable HCWs. However, some HCWs felt that this did not fall under the purview of their role because there was "not much time and scope at the moment to discuss other things other than the surgery they're

facing" and that not all HCWs recommended vaccination to patients. Some HCWs felt uncomfortable with the idea of trying to convince people who weren't in their immediate family because they believed everyone had the right to make their own decisions. However, if friends, co-workers, or patients asked them directly, many said they would explain why they chose to get vaccinated.

Type of Covid-19 vaccine received

According to the graph above, of the 200 participants (100%) who completed the form, 130 (65%) received AstraZeneca/Oxford products, Johnson & Johnson, 14% (7%). Pfizer/BioNTech and Moderna According to a policy review, the two-dose vaccination effectiveness for the Oxford-AstraZeneca and Pfizer vaccines was 70.4% and 95%, respectively, in phase III clinical trials. However, this finding did not line up with a research conducted in the UK by Anna Dowrick and colleagues.

Adverse effect of Covid-19 vaccine

The graph above shows that out of the 200 (100%) responders, 144 (72.3%) reported adverse reactions to the vaccination, ranging from mild to severe, while 56 (27.7%) reported no adverse reactions at all. This is comparable to a research by Peter C. Oriji, conducted in the south of Nigeria, which revealed that 9 out of every 10 health professionals who got the vaccination reported experiencing negative side effects.

Public enlightenment and grass- root awareness

Out of the 200 (100%) respondents, 183 (91.5%) agreed that it was a good idea to raise public awareness and educate the public through the media, advertisements, and other means to encourage the general populace to accept and implement the vaccine; however, 17 (8.5%) of the respondents disagreed with the idea. This is related to a study conducted in Delta state of Nigeria which revealed that there was an overall favourable attitude toward the COVID-19 vaccines.

4. CONCLUSION

Based on the results obtained from the analysis of the data the following conclusions were drawn, out of the 200 questionnaire that were distributed with 100% response

Most of the respondents 120(60%) were community vaccine recipients, whereas 24(12%) received their vaccine in Asokoro District Hospital and 21(10.5%) received the vaccine in Nyanya General Hospital.

Almost all the respondents 191(94.5%) believe that Covid-19 exist, whereas 9(4.5%) believe is a hoax and can't thrive in the tropics

Majority of the respondents 179(89.5%) perceive that Covid-19 is a global challenge,

Most of the respondents 106(53%) have been exposed to persons that confirmed to have contracted Covid-19 or even died of the virus.

Study shows that. Majority of the respondents 130(65%) received AstraZeneca/Oxford, 10(5%) Johnson & Johnson, 14(7%) Moderna and Pfizer/BioNTech

5. RECOMMENDATIONS

National primary health care development agency should work hand in hand with the Asokoro District Hospital/Nyanya general hospital to seek the political well to increase the Covid-19 vaccine rollout and to encourage vaccination of the populace.

Covid-19 Vaccine should be made available and accessible including the booster to encourage the vaccination in order to curb the spread of the disease in federal capital territory.

Media Such as television and radio should be used to inform and encourage the federal capital territory and it environ about the Covid-19 vaccine and its safety.

The international bodies such as World Health Organizations(W.H.O), United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF) and other Non-Governmental Organizations(NGOs) should help the federal capital territory (FCT) with the Covid-19 vaccine and also policies on how to get populace of the federal capital territory vaccinated.

Nigerian government at the ministry of health and state ministry of health should make policies and implement them, on how to go about vaccinating people with Covid-19 vaccine.

6. References

- Adejumo, O.A., Ogundele, O.A., Madubuko, C.R., Oluwafemi, R.O., Okoye, O.C., and Okonkwo, K.C. (2021). *Perceptions of the COVID-19 vaccine and willingness to receive vaccination among health workers in Nigeria. Osong Public Health and Research Perspectives*. 2021;12(4):236. doi: 10.24171/j.phrp.2021.0023. pmid:34289295. Accessed 12th November 2022.
- Africanews. NEWS. *Ethiopia launches Covid vaccination in Addis Ababa*. (2021). Available from: <https://www.africanews.com/2021/03/14/ethiopia-launches-covid-vaccinations-in-addis-ababa>. Accessed 18th November 2022.
- African Vaccine Acquisition Trust delivers 108,000 doses of COVID-19 vaccine to Ethiopia – Africa CDC [Internet]. 2021. Available from: <https://africacdc.org/news-item/african-vaccine-acquisition-trust-delivers-108,000-doses-of-covid-19-vaccine-to-ethiopia>. Accessed 18th November 2022.
- Alhassan, R.K., Aberese-Ako, M., Doegah, P.T., Immurana, M., Dalaba, M.A., and Manyeh, A.K. (2021). *COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy among the adult population in Ghana: evidence from a pre-vaccination rollout survey. Tropical Medicine and Health*. 2021;49(1):1–13. doi: 10.1186/s41182-020-00291-y. pmid:33397511. Accessed 12 November 2022
- Al-Qerem, W.A., and Jarab, A.S. (2021). *COVID-19 Vaccination Acceptance and Its Associated Factors Among a Middle Eastern Population*. *Front. Public Health*. 2021; 9:632914. doi: 10.3389/fpubh.2021.632914. pmid:33643995 Accessed on 25th April 2022.
- Bante, A., Mersha, A., Tesfaye, A., Tsegaye, B., Shibiru, S., and Ayele, G. (2021). *Adherence with COVID-19 Preventive Measures and Associated Factors Among Residents of Dirashe District, Southern Ethiopia*. *Patient Preference Adherence*. 2021; 15:237–249. doi: 10.2147/PPA.S293647. pmid:33568900 Accessed on 12th April 2022.
- Baloch, S., Baloch, M.A., Zheng, T., and Pei, X. (2019). *The coronavirus disease 2019 (COVID-19) pandemic*. *Tohoku J Exp Med*. 2020;250(4):271–278. – PubMed. Accessed 25th November 2022.

- Corey, L., Mascola, J.R., Fauci, A.S., and Collins, F.S. (2022). *A strategic approach to COVID-19 vaccine R&D*. *Science*. 2020;368(6494):948-950. PubMed | Google Scholar. Accessed 18 November 2022.
- Daly, M., and Robinson, E. (2021). *Willingness to vaccinate against COVID-19 in the US: representative longitudinal evidence from April to October 2020*. *American journal of preventivmedicine*.2021;60(6):766–73. doi: 10.1016/j.amepre.2021.01.008. pmid:33773862 Accessed on 12th April 2022
- Different COVID-19 Vaccines* | CDC. (2019). Accessed on 14th April 2022.from: <https://www.cdc.gov/coronavirus/2019-ncov/vaccines/different-vaccines.html>.*The push for a COVID-19 vaccine*. Accessed on 11th April 2022.from: https://www.who.int/emergencies/diseases/novel-coronavirus-2019/covid19vaccines?gclid=Cj0KCQjw2or8BRCNARIsAC_ppyYWO0oDbvpd9sqLLJWdKFEjk55hNRAlI DrsejAc9bXJtb4lzTWr5F8aAoa8EALw_wcB. 14.
- Ethiopia: *cumulative coronavirus cases (2021)*. Statista. Accessed on 12th April 2022. from: <https://www.statista.com> >... > State of Health. 10.1155/2021/5549893. pmid:340358187. Accessed on 24th April 2022
- Hager, E., Odetokun, I.A., Bolarinwa, O., Zainab, A., Okechukwu, O., and Al-Mustapha, A.I. (2019). *Knowledge, attitude, and perceptions towards the 2019 Coronavirus Pandemic: A bi-national survey in Africa*. PloS one. 2020;15(7):e0236918. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0236918. pmid:32726340. Accessed on 12th April 2022.
- Head, K.J., Kasting, M.L., Sturm, L.A., Hartsock, J.A., Zimet, G.D., and Obi, P. A. (2021). *COVID-19 vaccine hesitancy and willingness to pay: Emergent factors from a cross-sectional study in Nigeria(2021)*. Accessed on 13rd June 2022.
- Peter, C., Oriji, Dennis, O., and Allagoa, L. O. (2021). *Side effects profile of Covid-19 vaccine among health workers in a tertiary health institution in south south Nigeria 2021* 19th. Accessed on July 2022.
- World Health Organization, (WHO). (2021). *Coronavirus disease (COVID-19) Dashboard*, 2021. Available: <https://covid19.who.int/> [Accessed 30 Oct 2021].Google Scholar. Accessed 12th May 2022.
- A new coronavirus associated with human respiratory disease in China*. *Nature*. (2020). 579(7798):265–9. doi: 10.1038/s41586-020-2008-pmid:32015508; Accessed on 24th November 2022.
- Yaqub, O., Castle-Clarke, S., and Sevdalis, N. (2014). *Attitudes to vaccination: a critical review*. *Soc Sci Med* 2014;112:1–11.doi:10.1016/j.socscimed.2014.04.018pmid:http://www.ncbi.nlm.ni

h.gov/pubmed/24788111CrossRefPubMedGoogle Scholar. Accessed
23rd April 2022.

Zelege, G., Saba, G., Melaku, A., Alemu, G., Genet, M., and Melkam, T. (2021). *The Escalating Magnitude of COVID-19 Infections among the Northeastern Ethiopia Region: A Community-Based Cross-Sectional Study*. International Journal of Microbiology. 2021.

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